

Investigating Performance Benefits from OpenACC Kernel Directives

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Abstract

This whitepaper explores the possible benefit of using OpenACC performance tuning directives, comparing the two prevalent implementations of the standard, CAPS and PGI. The performance of the default generated code along with the impact of the gang and vector parameters is evaluated through a matrix-matrix multiplication and a Classical Gram-Schmidt orthonormalization. Additionally, the impact in the context of a change in the hardware is assessed.

1. Introduction

A current trend in High Performance Computing is the adoption of GPU accelerators used for offloading computation from a host CPU to the GPU device. GPUs are equipped with a large number of small and efficient cores providing large amounts of low power computation on the order of Teraflops from a single GPU [1]. Programming for these can be a challenge, as it is important that memory access and loop scheduling are handled sensibly to obtain good performance. Due to this difficulty, many less experienced HPC users tend to avoid the use of GPUs. Experienced users can also be reluctant to adopt these devices, as porting existing code can be a difficult task, and keeping programs portable and up to date can be time consuming.

The concerns about GPU programmability have been recognised by many users and vendors in the field of HPC. In response, a number of new programming models have been developed to reduce the difficulty of programming for GPUs and other heterogeneous systems. These models include OpenHMPP, R-Stream, PGI Accelerator, OpenACC, and more [2-6]. OpenACC has been receiving positive attention, as it is the first attempt at a directive based GPU programming standard, supported by CAPS, CRAY, PGI, and NVIDIA [6]. While OpenACC provides a simpler GPU programming model than alternatives such as CUDA and OpenCL [7-8], some low level control is surrendered to the compiler in the hope that it can automatically produce good performance.

In this report, the use of OpenACC for loop scheduling is explored to investigate how the parallel performance can be best optimised. This will be done using the PGI, and CAPS implementations of the standard, which are similar to the pre-existing PGI Accelerator and OpenHMPP model developed independently by PGI and CAPS respectively. OpenACC provides similar functionality to PGI Accelerator and OpenHMPP, however now it is all under a common standard.

1.1 OpenACC Programming Model

OpenACC is a high level programming language extension that makes use of directives to indicate regions of code to be run on an acceleration device. This attempts to replace the CUDA and OpenCL programming models where kernels and data transfers are written explicitly.

The four directive constructs available are **data**, **kernels**, **parallel**, and **loop**. The **data** construct allows the developer to specify how memory transfers between the host and the acceleration device are handled. For example, if a variable is only read and not modified within an accelerated region, a **copyin** clause could be used to ensure this variable is not copied back to the host upon completion. If the **data** construct is not used, this behaviour will be handled automatically.

The **kernels** construct is used to specify a region of code for which parallel execution will take place. The compiler automatically identifies the parallelisable loops within this region, and generates kernels that are run in parallel on the accelerator.

The **parallel** construct indicates a region of code that is to be launched in parallel on the acceleration device. This code will run identically on multiple accelerator threads until a **loop** region is encountered, at which point a subset of the total iterations will be executed on each thread [9].

Finally, the **loop** construct is used within the **kernels** and **parallel** constructs, specifying that a region contains a work-sharing **loop**. In a **kernels** region this is used to help the compiler with automatic parallelisation. In the **parallel** region, a **loop** directive is required if any work sharing is to take place.

These directives take the form of:

```
C/C++:      #pragma acc (directive-name) [[,] clause[clause ..]
Fortran:    !$acc (directive-name) [clause[.,] clause ..]
```

with a number of clauses available. Further details can be found in the OpenACC Standard available online [5].

2. Design and Implementation

In this report, the performance tuning options of OpenACC were explored for a matrix-matrix multiplication code, and a Classical Gram-Schmidt orthonormalization, using the CAPS and PGI compilers. As the CAPS compiler only handles regions of code intended for the accelerator, the Intel compiler was used in conjunction with CAPS to generate code for the CPU.

The purpose of these tests was to identify if stating values for the **gang** and **vector** clauses could improve the performance of loop scheduling behaviour. These values allow the user to modify how a region is parallelised. Specifically, the **gang** value describes the coarse-grained parallelism for each loop, similar to the number of thread blocks in CUDA terminology, and the **vector** clause dictates the fine grained parallelism, specifying the number of threads within each gang [10].

There is an additional clause called **worker** that is quite similar to gang and vector values as it can be used to specify how to parallelise a given region. This clause was omitted from these experiments as it was only supported by one of the compilers when running these tests and its distinction from the vector value was not clear.

2.1 Matrix-Matrix Multiply

The matrix-matrix multiply implementation used a naïve multiplication with $O(N^3)$ complexity with arrays of 8000x8000 floating-point numbers. The OpenACC parallelisation was performed using a **kernels loop independent** directive on the outermost loop of the multiplication operation as seen in Figure 1. The **independent** clause was used to guarantee to the compiler that there were no dependencies. The outermost loop was parallelised using a **gang** clause, and the middle loop used a **vector** clause. Finally a **loop sequential** directive was used on the innermost loop to enforce order, as floating-point arithmetic is not associative.

This behaviour could also be handled by adding a **gang** and **vector** clause inline with the **kernels** directive, however the PGI and CAPS compilers handled this information differently in some cases. By assigning **gang** and **vector** values directly to each loop, consistent behaviour was found between compilers for all cases.

2.2 Gram-Schmidt Orthonormalization

A Classical Gram-Schmidt (CGS) orthonormalization code based on an example by Rob Farber [11] was examined using an array size of 2000x2000 floating-point numbers. This operation was of $O(N^2)$ complexity and contained a number of parallel loops with various levels of nesting, which differs from the matrix-matrix multiplication as all computation for this example existed inside a single loop. The CGS program was parallelised using the **parallel loop** directive, which is similar to the **kernels loop** directive however it can spawn additional kernels within the parallel region. **Gang** and **vector** sizes are specified within this directive using **vector_size** and **gang_num** clauses.

Figure 1 – Serial and OpenACC implementations of the matrix-matrix multiply

Serial:

```
for(i=0; i<SIZE; i++){
    for(j=0; j<SIZE; j++){
        for(k=0; k<SIZE; k++){
            c[i*SIZE+j] += a[i*SIZE+k]*b[k*SIZE+j];
        }
    }
}
```

OpenACC:

```
#pragma acc kernels loop independent gang(256)
{
    for(i=0; i<SIZE; i++){
        #pragma acc loop vector(512)
        for(j=0; j<SIZE; j++){
            #pragma acc loop seq
            for(k=0; k<SIZE; k++){
                c[i*SIZE+j] += a[i*SIZE+k]*b[k*SIZE+j];
            }
        }
    }
}
```

2.3 Testing Process

For both codes, initial measurements were taken for the serial runtime with both compilers. A shared memory implementation was then run with four threads on a quad-core processor using OpenMP directives for parallelisation. These two runtimes served as a comparison for results from OpenACC and a GPU device. As the CAPS compiler specifically handles the GPU code, the Intel compiler was used to generate code for the host device. As such, the Intel compiler was used to obtain serial runtimes for the CAPS compiled OpenACC implementation, and the PGI compiler was used for the PGI implementation.

Once the serial and shared memory runtimes were established, GPU testing began. As the aim was to identify the ideal scheduling values for performance, a systematic sweep of **gang** and **vector** values was taken to identify a minimum point. Values were varied until a clear minimum could be identified, or values had reached their maximum or minimum limit. These results were then tested on a different hardware platform to explore this behaviour.

2.4 Test Platforms

Serial and shared memory runtimes were measured using an Intel 2.8GHz Xeon X5560 quad-core processor with 6GB of RAM available per core. The shared memory implementations made use of four threads on the quad-core processor. OpenACC tests were taken using the Xeon X5560 and an NVIDIA Tesla M2090 GPU. Further testing was also performed on the NVIDIA Tesla K20 GPU, however due to licensing restrictions this was only performed using the CAPS compiler. Compilers and modules used the following versions; PGI v12.8, CAPS v3.3.1, Intel v2011.9.293, and CUDA 5.0.

3. Performance Results

3.1 Matrix-Matrix Multiply

The runtime of the matrix-matrix multiplication was taken using multiple hardware platforms, hardware configurations, and loop scheduling options. These can be seen in Figures 2 and 3, and Tables 1 and 2.

Figure 2 – Matrix-matrix multiply runtimes for different gang and vector sizes compiled using PGI and run on an NVIDIA M2090 GPU

Figure 3 – Matrix-matrix multiply runtimes for different gang and vector sizes compiled using CAPS run on an NVIDIA M2090 GPU

Table 1 – Runtimes for different implementations of the matrix-matrix multiply using the PGI compiler

Implementation	Hardware	Runtime
Serial	Intel Xeon X5560	311.9s
OpenMP (4 Threads)	Quad-Core Intel Xeon X5560	81.0s
OpenACC automatic	Intel Xeon X5560 /NVIDIA M2090	39.1s
OpenACC gang (64) vector (256)	Intel Xeon X5560 /NVIDIA M2090	22.6s

Table 2 – Runtimes for different implementations of the matrix-matrix multiply using the CAPS compiler

Implementation	Hardware	Runtime
Serial	Intel Xeon X5560	207.0s
OpenMP (4 Threads)	Quad-Core Intel Xeon X5560	82.5s
OpenACC automatic	Intel Xeon X5560 /NVIDIA M2090	65.3s
OpenACC gang (1024) vector (256)	Intel Xeon X5560 /NVIDIA M2090	21.0s
OpenACC gang (1024) vector (512)	Intel Xeon X5560 /NVIDIA M2090	21.3s
OpenACC automatic	Intel Xeon E5-2643 / NVIDIA K20	17.3s
OpenACC gang (1024) vector (256)	Intel Xeon E5-2643 / NVIDIA K20	17.8s
OpenACC gang (1024) vector (512)	Intel Xeon E5-2643 / NVIDIA K20	16.2s

3.1.1 PGI Compiler

When using the PGI compiler, the matrix-matrix multiplication was measured to have a serial runtime of 311.9s, and a runtime of 81.0s when run using OpenMP with four threads on a quad-core processor. The automatic OpenACC compiler values provided a **vector** length of 128 with an unspecified **gang** size, resulting in a runtime of 39.1s. The minimum OpenACC runtime on the NVIDIA M2090 was obtained using a **gang** size of 64, and a **vector** size of 256. This provided in a runtime of 22.6s. This was a factor of 13.8 times faster than the serial version, 3.6 times faster than the shared memory implementation, and 1.7 times faster than the automatic OpenACC parallelisation. The various **gang** and **vector** runtimes can be seen in Figure 2 and Table 1.

3.1.2 CAPS Compiler

When using the CAPS compiler in conjunction with Intel’s compiler, the matrix-matrix multiplication resulted in a serial runtime of 207.0s, and a shared memory runtime of 82.5s when run with four threads on a quad-core processor. When run on an NVIDIA M2090 GPU, the automatic OpenACC compiler provided a **vector** size of 128 with a **gang** size of 32, with a runtime of 65.3s. The optimal OpenACC performance was obtained using a **gang** size of 1024, and a **vector** size of 256. This resulted in a runtime of 21.0s. This was a factor of 9.9 times faster than the serial version, 3.9 times faster than the shared memory implementation, and 3.1 times faster than the automatic OpenACC parallelisation. The performance for the various **gang** and **vector** values can be seen in Figure 3 and Table 2.

Further tests were performed using the NVIDIA K20 GPU. On this platform, the automatic behaviour resulted in a runtime of 17.3s. When the optimal values from the M2090 were used on the K20 with a **gang** size of 1024 and **vector** size of 256, a runtime of 17.8s was measured. Further testing showed the optimal K20 performance occurred with a **gang** size of 1024, and a **vector** size of 512 with a runtime of 16.2s.

3.2 Matrix-Matrix Multiply Discussion

3.2.1 PGI Compiler

From the results obtained in this experiment, it was seen that adding the optimal **gang** and **vector** values to the OpenACC directives provided a factor of 1.7 faster performance over the automatic OpenACC parallelisation. Overall it was seen that a **vector** size of between 256 and 512 provided the optimal runtimes for this example.

It can also be seen from Figure 2 that the **gang** value had no clear impact on the performance. While not mentioned in the documentation, it is likely that PGI is automatically handling one of these dimensions to fit the number of iterations more ideally to the problem size.

3.2.2 CAPS Compiler

The experiments from the CAPS compiler on the NVIDIA M2090 showed that the addition of optimal **gang** and **vector** directives resulted in a faster runtime than the automatic OpenACC case by a factor of 3.1. This is a significant improvement. It can be seen from results in Figure 3 that both the **gang** and the **vector** values had a clear impact on performance.

It was also noted that the serial runtime of the matrix-matrix multiplication using the Intel compiler was a factor 1.5 faster than the serial PGI implementation. This is likely due to Intel’s optimisation capabilities on their own hardware. As the shared memory runtimes were very similar between both compilers however, these results do not affect the validity of the performance comparisons.

Additional tests were performed with the CAPS compiler on the NVIDIA K20 GPU which confirmed that the **gang** and **vector** tuning was useful for exploiting specific architectures. In these tests, the automatic scheduling resulted in a runtime of 17.3s, the optimal values from the M2090 tests provided a slower runtime of 17.8s, and the optimal K20 runtime was found to be 16.2s. This was carried out by increasing the **vector** size to match the hardware, with a **gang** size of 1024 and a **vector** size of 512.

3.3 Classical Gram-Schmidt

The performance of the Classical Gram-Schmidt orthonormalization was measured using multiple hardware configurations and loop scheduling options. These can be seen in Figures 4 and 5, and Tables 3 and 4.

Figure 4 – CGS runtime results for different gang and vector sizes compiled using PGI and run on an M2090 GPU

Figure 5 – CGS runtime results for different gang and vector sizes compiled using CAPS and run on an M2090 GPU

Table 3 – Runtimes for different implementations of the CGS orthonormalization using the PGI compiler

Implementation	Hardware	Runtime
Serial	Intel Xeon X5560	13.8s
OpenMP (4 Threads)	Quad-Core Intel Xeon X5560	3.9s
OpenACC automatic	Intel Xeon X5560 /NVIDIA M2090	2.0s
OpenACC num_gangs(256) vector_size(256)	Intel Xeon X5560 /NVIDIA M2090	2.0s

Table 4 – Runtimes for different implementations of the CGS orthonormalization using the CAPS compiler

Implementation	Hardware	Runtime
Serial	Intel Xeon X5560	8.9s
OpenMP (4 Threads)	Quad-Core Intel Xeon X5560	3.0s
OpenACC automatic	Intel Xeon X5560 /NVIDIA M2090	2.9s
OpenACC num_gangs(512) vector_size(512)	Intel Xeon X5560 /NVIDIA M2090	2.7s

3.3.1 PGI Compiler

When using the PGI compiler, the CGS orthonormalization provided a serial runtime of 13.8s, and a runtime of 3.9s when run using four threads on a quad-core processor. The OpenACC automatic scheduling resulted in a runtime of 2.0s, with a variety of parameters for the multiple loops throughout the code. Overall, the automatic values were found to be the fastest scheduling option for running on the NVIDIA M2090. The fastest manually assigned parameters were found to be **num_gangs(256)** and **vector_size(256)** which matched the automatic runtime at 2.0s. The runtimes of various scheduling options can be seen in Figure 4 and Table 3.

3.3.2 CAPS Compiler

When using the CAPS compiler in conjunction with Intel's compiler, the CGS orthonormalization resulted in a serial runtime of 8.9s, and a runtime of 3.0s with four threads on a quad-core processor. When using the NVIDIA M2090 GPU, the automatic OpenACC scheduling resulted in a runtime of 2.9s. The optimal OpenACC performance was obtained using a **num_gangs** and **vector_size** value of 512 giving a runtime of 2.7s. The various **gang** and **vector** runtimes from these tests can be seen in Figure 5 and Table 4.

Results on the K20 for this example were inconclusive due to very long runtimes with unknown cause. This was likely due to both the OpenACC standard and the K20 architecture being quite new. As such, some bugs were to be expected.

3.4 Classical Gram-Schmidt Discussion

3.4.1 PGI Compiler

It was seen that the automatic OpenACC loop scheduling behaviour provided the best performance for the PGI compiled CGS orthonormalization with a runtime of 2.0s, which is a speedup of 1.9 over the shared memory implementation. This suggests the **parallel** construct may provide more ideal loop scheduling than the **kernels** directive. The testing also revealed that performance is strongly related to **num_gang** and **vector_length** values, with many scheduling options resulting in runtimes similar to that of the serial CPU implementation. This results can be avoided by ensuring the **num_gang** and **vector_length** values are chosen to be larger than 128.

3.4.2 CAPS Compiler

The CAPS compiler results showed that the automatic OpenACC scheduling with a runtime of 2.9s was not the optimal behaviour, however the fastest runtime of 2.7s was not dramatically improved compared to the results seen in the matrix-matrix multiply. Additionally, when both the **num_gang** and **vector_length** values were below 128, the performance was particularly poor. These results suggest that large **num_gang** and **vector_length** values provide better performance, and that the **parallel** construct may provide better loop scheduling behaviour than the use of **kernels**.

4. Conclusion

The runtime of two algorithms, matrix-matrix multiplication and Classical Gram-Schmidt, were investigated with a variety of OpenACC performance tuning parameters using the PGI and CAPS compilers on an NVIDIA M2090 GPU. For the case of matrix-matrix multiplication it was demonstrated that by explicitly choosing **gang** and **vector** values to match GPU architecture improvement in runtimes over the automatic scheduling can be obtained. Choosing optimal values for these parameters was seen to provide a speedup of 1.7 and 3.1 for the PGI and CAPS compilers respectively when compared to the automatic OpenACC parallelisation. It was also demonstrated that the NVIDIA K20 GPU has different optimal values than the NVIDIA M2090 as is to be expected when considering their different architectures.

The Classical Gram-Schmidt example revealed that when using the **parallel loop** directive, the automatic compiler behaviour was seen to be optimal when compiled using PGI, and very close to optimal when using CAPS. It was also demonstrated that there is a wide variety of scheduling options which result in much poorer performance, re-enforcing the need for well chosen parameters. The results from both the matrix-matrix multiplication and CGS orthonormalization suggest that nearly ideal performance can be reached simply by ensuring **gang** and **vector** values both are larger than 128.

While OpenACC is a relatively new standard, it already provides access to GPU accelerators without requiring any major coding effort. The directive-based programming model is simple to implement, and allows for incremental parallelisation without breaking the functionality of the serial program. With some additional work toward finding the ideal loop scheduling parameters, it was demonstrated that it is possible to increase performance by a factor of up to 3.1 times the performance of the automatic parallelisation for the algorithms that were investigated.

Finally, it was demonstrated that the PGI and CAPS compilers showed very similar performance with their ideal OpenACC implementations, although there were some differences in the handling of directives and automatic behaviour. As this is the first release of the standard, some inconsistencies in the handling of directives are to be expected. As the standard matures, the performance tuning options available will continue to be an interesting area of work.

Acknowledgements

This work was financially supported by the PRACE-2IP project funded in part by the EU's 7th Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) under grant agreement no. RI-283493. The work was carried out in collaboration with ICHEC using the Stoney and Johannes systems.

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